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Study of Achievement Motivation in Relation to Academic Achievement in the Context of Basic Education

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Abstract: This study has explored the learner's achievement motivation in relation to academic performance in identified school in Borbon District. This study employed descriptive survey method Quantitative approach was employed to answer all the research questions covered in this study. Based on the finding of the study, the grade 4,5 and 6 learners have very high level of achievement motivation. In terms of their academic performance, it is equivalent to 82.37 which means approaching proficiency. While, the learner's high level of achievement motivation is not associated with their academic performance. There is significant degree of variances in the level of achievement motivation when grouped according to their grade levels. The results implied that achievement motivation assessment be concluded regularly to intermediate learners to gauge their readiness to new and bigger academic tasks. Moreover, teacher of schools should employ strategies that provide learners to experience, discover and master the concepts across disciplines.

Keywords: Academic Motivation, Academic Achievement, Basic Education

1. Introduction

Learning is a knowledge or skill acquired through study or by being taught. A child's capacity to learn may be seen in how he or she reacts to and makes sense of the world around them and the information presented to them (Driver et al., 2014). A student's success in school depends on several factors: their instructors, the quality of their classroom and learning environment, the curriculum they follow, the support they get from their parents, the books they read, and most importantly, their study habits (Robinson, 2000).

Educational psychologists and researchers have argued that there are many determinants of academic performance, one of them being achievement motivation (Wigfield, 2000). Previous theorists have focused on achievement goals,

conceptualized as situationally specific measures of motivational orientation, and argued that they may be stronger predictors of academic success (Pintrich & Schunk, 1996). Achievement goals reflect the purpose of achievement behavior in a particular setting (Dweck & Leggett, 1988; Nicholls, 1984). When pursuing mastery goals in a learning situation, a student's purpose is to develop competence by acquiring new knowledge and skills. When pursuing performance goals, a student's purpose is to demonstrate competence relative to others. Not all students are positively oriented toward competence, however, and some adopt work avoidance goals that focus on effort minimization (Yeh et al., 2019)

Another goal of the present research was to examine the interplay of ability, prior performance, and achievement motivation in predicting the specific achievement goals that students adopt in their classes. Previous research has examined how individual differences in achievement motivation can predispose students to adopt particular goals in a classroom (Ejiobi-Okee & Samuel, 2019). Moreover, one of the most important factors that lead one to their goals is the drive. This drive is known as motivation. It is a zest and determination with a kind of excitement that leads one to persevere to reach greater heights, in no matter what avenue of their life; be it personal or professional (Singh, 2011). Motivation is generally regarded as the drive to achieve targets and the process to maintain the drive. Motivation provides an important foundation to complete cognitive behavior, such as planning, organization, decision-making, learning, and assessments. Argyris, (1960) defined achievements as task-oriented behavior. Performances of individuals are often compared against standards or with others for assessments.

The differing perspectives of scholars result in various definitions of achievement motivation. The original definition of achievement motivation was from Blyth, & Foster-Clark, (1987) who defined it as the comparison of performances with others and against certain standard activities. Bureau of Labor Statistics. (1999) suggested that achievement motivation is a combination of two personality variables: tendency to approach success and tendency to avoid failure. Bornholt & Goodnow (1999) defined achievement motivation as the drive to work with diligence and vitality, to constantly steer toward targets, to obtain dominance in challenging and difficult tasks and create sense of achievement as a result. This definition consists of three elements: the stimulation of personal capabilities, constant efforts with drive and obtaining of sense of satisfaction. Rounds & Gorney (1992). Consolidated the theories concerning achievement motivation and compiled the Work and Family Orientation Questionnaire (WOFO). Meanwhile, they conducted a factor analysis and argued that achievement motivation consists of four elements, i.e., mastery of needs, work orientation, competition, and personal unconcern. After further studies, they found that the interaction of the first three elements is the key reason that contributes to excellent performance of individuals. It is highly related to personal achievements.

Academic achievement is one of the most important indicators of learning and understanding in all educational systems. It is undoubtedly research after the heart of many educational psychologists, who make an attempt to investigate what determines academic outcomes of learners (Rahmani, 2011). According to Adeyinka et al. (2011),

the attainment of success by a student in his school work among his classmates is termed academic achievement. Kpolovie et al. (2014), defined academic achievement as the ability of a student to study and remember facts and being able to communicate his knowledge orally or in written form even in an examination condition. The authors also opined that academic achievement is a measurable index that depicts a student's cognitive, affective and psychomotor domains in educational setting.

Academic achievement, as defined by Obi and Oguzie (2018), is an individual's level of performance on mental challenges. He clarified that it was the kids' overall academic potential as measured against an unspecified "pass mark." In the following, I will use the term "academic accomplishment" to refer to the quantifiable outcomes of a student's efforts to acquire and apply knowledge and skills across a range of relevant and rigorous assessments (Joe et al., 2014).

The term "academic achievement" is often used to refer to a person's level of success on standardized tests and other measures of school performance. It may also be seen in terms of the final educational accomplishments of a person (Gbonee, 2014). Aryana (2010) found that pupils who did well academically were more likely to report feeling persuaded and pleased than those who did poorly. Students who do well in school often have a healthy sense of self-confidence, whereas those who struggle tend to underachieve.

According to Squier (2016), academic achievement is sometimes viewed as the amount of content learned by students. It is measured by intelligence (example Intelligence quotient) and standardized tests in core subject areas (example mathematics, chemistry, physics). Academic achievement is mostly measured using examinations or continuous assessment but there is no conclusive agreement on how best it is tested or which aspect are most necessary. The differences in academic achievements can be attributed to various factors like intelligence, creativity, self-esteem, cognitive style, achievement motivation, instructional strategy, self-efficacy, personality and many others (Sharma & Pooja, 2018). Since there are many factors that play an important role to promote or decline academic achievement, some of these factors which include achievement motivation, locus of control and many others are very essential to be recognized and used to improve the academic achievements of students.

Moreover, achievement motivation is an individual's ability to desire strongly success in general or in a specified discipline. Achievement motivation as posited by Chetri (2014) is the attitude to achieve rather than the achievements themselves. It can be considered as an extended person-intrinsic motivation because its reinforcement is delayed. It arises from an interaction within the person. It is also a pattern of planning of actions and of feeling connected with striving to achieve some internalized standard of excellence (Chetri, 2014; Suson et al., 2020). Achievement motivation as a desire to accomplish something difficult, to overcome obstacles and attain a high standard, to excel oneself. He indicated that high achievement motivated students are moderate risk takers and have an energetic approach to work. In other words, it is a motivation to achieve, a person's desire to succeed or complete a task successfully. Achievement motivation can be linked to Locus of control as it relates to people's attitudes, emotions

and motivation, as well as behaviour in organizations and educational institutions (Spector & Fox, 2005).

In the Philippines particularly in Amancio Sepulveda Elementary School, teachers observed that pupils with low achievement motivation are most likely the ones who fare poorly in their academic subjects. The researcher, being a school head in Amancio Sepulveda Elementary School, was conducting this study in the hope that the data and findings will shed light on how behavioral problem impact pupil's academic performance.

2. Purpose of the Study

This research study determined the achievement motivation of the learners in relation to their academic performance. Specifically, it addressed the level of academic motivation among the respondents, and the academic performance. The significant correlation between achievement motivation and academic performance was also treated.

3. Research Methodology

This study employed descriptive survey method to determine the pupils' achievement motivation in relation to their scholastic achievement. The study was conducted at Amancio Elementary School, located in the Municipality of Borbon, Borbon Cebu, Northern part of Cebu Province. Moreover, the respondents were composed of the following pupils: 57 males and 35 females with a total of 92. The instruments of the study in terms of achievement motivation have 18 questions which are answerable by the teachers, while for the scholastic achievement, data was taken based on the learner's performance.

4. Results and Discussions

Table 1
Level of Achievement Motivation among the Learners

Grade Level	Mean	Verbal Description
Grade 4	3.86	Very High
Grade 5	3.82	Very High
Grade 6	3.74	Very High

Table 1 present the data in terms of the level of achievement motivation among the Learners. Data shows that the grade 4,5 and 6 learners have very high level of achievement motivation, this indicates that they have high need and desire to achieve in educational endeavors for them to finish their schooling and ultimately find a job or pursue a stable career.

Based on the table 2, data shows that among the grade levels, grade 6 or level 6 learners got the highest weighted mean of 82.63 which verbally describe as approaching proficiency, followed by grade 4 with 82.54 which also verbally described as approaching proficiency and lastly, grade 5 got the lowest weighted mean of 81.89 which also verbally described as approaching proficiency.

Table 2
Academic Performance Among the Respondents

Grad 4		Grade 5		Grade 6	
No of Learners	Rating	No of Learners	Rating	No of Learners	Rating
1	83.85	1	83.95	1	79.05
2	85.00	2	79.50	2	88.00
3	87.00	3	80.40	3	79.40
4	79.60	4	80.25	4	83.55
5	79.45	5	79.05	5	82.00
6	80.75	6	82.80	6	79.75
7	79.80	7	87.15	7	85.00
8	86.00	8	78.65	8	85.65
9	81.00	9	85.25	9	81.25
10	82.95				
11	83.20				
12	81.90				
Sum	990.50		737.00		743.65
n	12		9		9
Mean	82.54		81.89		82.63

Table 3
Correlation between Achievement Motivation and Academic Performance

Res. No.	Achievement Motivation	Academic Performance	r	Critical Value of r at 28 df (0.05)	Results
Grade 4	3.86	82.54	0.07744	0.036184	Insignificant
Grade 5	3.82	81.89			
Grade 6	3.74	82.63			

It can be gleaned in the table that the computed r is 0.07744 and a critical value of 0.036184 higher than at 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the acceptance of the null hypothesis. Therefore, there is no significant relationship between the academic achievement of the learners and their academic performance.

Table 4
ANOVA on the Academic Achievement

Sources of Variation	df	Sum of Squares	Mean Squares	F-value	
				Computed	Tabular
Between Groups	2	0.06653	0.03327	6.50586	3.3500
Within Groups	27	0.1381	0.00511	Result: Significant	
Total	29	0.20459		Ho: Rejected	

It can be gleaned in the table that the computed f-value of 6.50586 and a critical value of 3.3500 is lower than at 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the rejection of the null hypothesis. Therefore, there is a significant degree of variance on the learner's achievement motivation when grouped according to grade level.

Table 5
Multiple Comparison Using Scheffe's Test

Between Groups	F'	F*K-1	Interpretation
G4 vs G5	1.23211	6.700	Insignificant
G4 vs G6	12.79268	6.700	Significant
G5 vs G6	5.3294	6.700	Insignificant

Based on the multiple comparison using the Scheffe's test, grade 4 and 5 learners achievement motivation do not differ significantly. The same results are proven between the achievement motivation of grades 5 and 6 learners. Between grade 4 and 6 learners, there is a significant degree of difference in their level of achievement motivation based on the multiple comparison using Scheffe's test.

Table 6
ANOVA on the academic performance

Sources of Variation	df	Sum of Squares	Mean Squares	F-value	
				Computed	Tabular
Between Groups	2	3.03481	1.51740	0.18339	3.3500
Within Groups	27	223.3986	8.27402	Result: Insignificant	
Total	29	226.43342		Ho: Accepted	

It can be gleaned in the table that the computed F-value of 0.18339 and a critical value of 3.3500 is lower than at 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the rejection of the null hypothesis. Therefore, there is a significant degree of variance on the learner's academic performance when grouped according to grade level.

Conclusions

Based on the finding of the study, the grade 4,5 and 6 learners have very high level of achievement motivation. In terms of their academic performance, it is equivalent to 82.37 which means approaching proficiency. While, the learner's high level of achievement motivation is not associated with their academic performance. There is significant degree of variances in the level of achievement motivation when grouped according to their grade levels. Therefore, the grade 4,5 and 6 learners differ in their level's achievement motivation. There is significant degree of differences between the level of achievement motivation of grade 4,5 and 6. Overall, there is no significant difference in the learner's academic performance when grouped to grade levels and between grade levels.

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